

Techniques for teaching English and enhancing writing and speaking abilities in non-philological students

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Abstract: In recent times, the training of experienced staff capable of meeting the demands of the current era has been identified as a crucial matter. The process of global integration has opened up avenues for the utilization of new educational technologies and vast educational expertise. Furthermore, leveraging advancements in science and technology, particularly in the realms of linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, psycholinguistics, and psychology, is essential for enhancing the efficacy of the educational process. An advantage of the innovative educational framework lies in its emphasis on cultivating high-achieving students' personal drive, unconventional thinking, accountability, proactiveness, and the cultivation of their unique perspectives on the world.

Keywords: creativity, competence, productive and analytical thinking pronunciation, tools, critical thinking.

Currently, one of the most crucial matters in the field of education pertains to the purpose, content, methods, tools, organizational forms, knowledge transmission, and achievement of educational objectives based on the subject matter studied during the educational process.

The emergence of new approaches and methods in language teaching has been influenced by various factors. However, these approaches and methods have failed to uncover the fundamental essence of teaching. Instead, they have only focused on teaching specific aspects of the language. No single theory, approach, or method encompasses all the comprehensive aspects of language teaching.

The effectiveness and productivity of teaching foreign languages in non-philological higher educational institutions is determined by the foreign language course of the host country and the distinctiveness of its structure, the age-specific traits of the students, the objectives set for this stage, the curriculum, and the psychological and pedagogical factors associated with the commencement of foreign language instruction at this level. The approach to teaching foreign languages in non-philological higher educational institutions is greatly influenced by the organization and implementation of instruction at the introductory level of higher education.

According to the scientific literature and methodical instructions regarding the differentiation of foreign language teaching stages in non-philological higher educational institutions, along with feedback from pedagogical practice and student observations during lessons, it is essential to consider the individual characteristics of students when selecting educational materials for the initial stage, specifically the first academic year. This includes tailoring methods for working with the material, creating exercises, and organizing lessons based on the student's unique traits. In simpler terms, all the aforementioned tasks should be conducted with consideration of the student's age and worldview. It should not be forgotten that reading is an activity based on hard work. Therefore, at the initial stage of higher education, in the formation of oral speech, that is, in the development of speech skills, it is necessary to try not to take and memorize the knowledge of students but to form them based on activities that require a certain amount of effort. Such an activity should be an activity that requires a certain initiative, mental and physical effort, that is,

movement. During this activity, students get used to their participation in the speech process, which creates a positive emotion in them and increases confidence in their abilities.

Several techniques can be used to teach English and enhance writing and speaking abilities in non-philological students. Here are a few suggestions:

- ❖ Communicative approach: Focus on communication skills rather than just grammar and vocabulary. Encourage students to engage in real-life conversations, role-plays, and group discussions to practice speaking and listening.

- ❖ Writing workshops: Provide opportunities for students to practice writing through guided exercises, peer editing, and feedback sessions. Encourage them to write essays, stories, emails, or journal entries regularly.

- ❖ Language games and activities: Use interactive games, puzzles, and activities to make learning English fun and engaging. This can help improve vocabulary retention and language skills enjoyably.

- ❖ Multimedia resources: Incorporate multimedia resources such as videos, podcasts, songs, and online platforms into your lessons to expose students to different accents, speech patterns, and styles of communication.

- ❖ Pronunciation drills: Focus on improving pronunciation through regular pronunciation drills, tongue twisters, and listening exercises. Encourage students to practice speaking out loud to build confidence in their speaking abilities.

- ❖ Vocabulary building: Help students expand their vocabulary by introducing new words in context through reading passages or listening exercises. Encourage them to use these words in spoken and written communication.

- ❖ Cultural immersion: Expose students to English-speaking cultures through literature, films, music, or cultural events. This can help broaden their understanding of the language and improve their overall language proficiency.

Overall, it's important to create a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable practicing their English skills without fear of making mistakes. Encouraging regular practice, providing constructive feedback, and offering personalized support can help non-philological students improve their writing and speaking abilities in English over time.

In the process of organizing foreign language teaching, in the analysis of the problem of the image of the external world in the human psychological imagination and its reflection in the language, it is one of the most urgent problems to check their language and speech reserves, the memory of the units gathered in them, and the factors of this in teaching foreign language learners to speak a foreign language. one is counted. These problems make it necessary to apply language and speech units in an associative direction in linguistics and foreign language teaching.

In conclusion, utilizing a variety of techniques for teaching English and enhancing writing and speaking abilities in non-philological students is essential for their language development. It is important to incorporate activities that cater to different learning styles, such as visual aids, interactive exercises, and real-life communication opportunities. Providing constructive feedback and encouragement can also greatly benefit students in improving their language skills. By creating a supportive and engaging learning environment, educators can help non-philological students build confidence in their writing and speaking abilities, ultimately leading to greater proficiency in the English language.

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